

How fragile is it? A GIS-based multicriteria assessment to define management priorities for a Mediterranean terraced system (Tuscany, Italy)

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Introduction

Terraced systems shape the surface water and soil management of many agricultural areas around the Mediterranean coasts (Pinto-Correia and Vos, 2004). Terraces, especially dry-stone terraces are probably the best-known example of the various agro-hydrological infrastructures that have been developed all over the world through centuries of agricultural activities. In particular, terraces and the like are anthropic modifications that have a permanent impact on the geomorphological stability due to the intense remodelling of steep slopes (Tarolli et al., 2014). By design, agro-hydrological infrastructures require both continuous anthropic action to maintain each component, and coordination between multiple actors to maintain the functioning of the overall system (Asins Velis, 2007).

Due to their poor machinability, many terraced systems have been partially abandoned or completely neglected in recent decades. However, portions of these systems located in peri-urban areas have the potential to transition to neo-rurality. There, newcomers purchase houses and land for settlement purposes, and then resume farming as a part-time or hobby activity, albeit with sporadic or incorrect management practices of the agro-hydrological infrastructures (Gennai-Schott et al., 2020; Van Eetvelde and Antrop, 2004). The mix of full-time, part-time, and hobby farmers underpins the evolution of the system management. To provide valuable support to these different land managers and develop new management strategies, the key challenge is to capitalize on prior knowledge about the individual agro-hydrological infrastructures and their place within the overall system (Tarolli et al., 2019).

Several studies and research projects have addressed the management of terraced system, covering various geographic locations and disciplinary or integrative approaches. However, the literature points out two needs yet to be addressed. On the one hand, the **co-design** of management, to involve heterogeneous land managers acting at different spatial levels with different purposes. On the other hand, the **re-design** of strategies and practices for agro-hydrological infrastructure management with a system approach. This paper discusses some lessons learned from a co-designed method aimed at supporting different actors and stakeholders in prioritising management practices of a terraced system located in the northern Mediterranean (Rizzo et al., 2022).

Description of the case study

The case study is located on the south-western hillside of Monte Pisano (43° 44' N - 10° 32' E, Tuscany, Italy). It was delimited within the administrative boundaries of the three municipalities participating in a series of research projects spanning approximately two decades (Rizzo and

- 1. It is necessary to evaluate the validity of the method.** Researchers in geographical sciences emphasise the need to associate validity metrics with the maps delivered to the decision-makers. In the case study, there was a further need to evaluate the validity of the fragility assessment itself. The notion of fragility was adopted because it was already used by land managers and local policy-makers. To operationalise it, it was important to achieve a shared definition and associate it to measurable criteria and attributes, and then classify it so that it could be used to design management strategies (Figure 1). This process allowed to define and prioritise the management issues of the terraced system as a whole, such as the lack of quantitative information about the various agro-hydrological infrastructures that compose it and of their spatial structure. Furthermore, the choice of a spatially explicit multicriteria decision analysis provided the required flexibility and modularity of choices throughout the method co-design process to integrate the perspectives of different actors.
- 2. Improving the communication of method validity** should complement the co-design process. Indeed, the method co-design process implies several simplifications or approximations of the description and formalisation of the agro-hydrological infrastructures and system to cope with the lack of specific data or to compromise the diverging perspectives of local actors. Hence, decision-makers should be made aware of the validity limits of the method and results for their decision-making process. For instance, this concerns the spatial and temporal scales at which the results are relevant, as well as their possible aggregation to address different levels of analysis. Indeed, validity is multifaceted and so are the relevant metrics for multicriteria models (Qureshi et al., 1999). These metrics include precision, which needs to be calibrated upon the expectations of different users, accuracy, for which spatial and temporal references could not be available, and reliability, which could be evaluated by repeating the assessment. Unfortunately, the multiplicity of the available metrics can be confusing.
- 3. Co-designing avoids the “black box” effect** for land managers and other local decision-makers involved in the process. The involvement of local decision-makers from the very beginning, i.e. from the definition of the decision-making problem, was intended to promote the shared definition and mutual understanding of the assessment choices (Barcellini et al., 2015). Moreover, this process ensured and improved the relevance of the results.
- 4. Improving the integration of local needs.** In the case study, the decision-makers expressed the need for fragility maps and a handbook to identify and disseminate management solutions. In this sense, the method co-design process supported the re-design of management strategies and practices from a system perspective. The local government adopted the results to improve the coordination for the terraced system management also because of the involvement of the local department of Civil Protection in the overall assessment process. The expected results were completed by a number of co-products of the method targeted to other stakeholders, such as a book on the history of the local terraced landscape, the design of a hiking trail to promote visits to key agro-hydrological infrastructures, and an economic evaluation of the various management practices (Galli et al., 2008; Gennai-Schott et al., 2020).

Conclusion

“How fragile is it?” was the question posed by the local land manager of the terraced system chosen as a case study for this work. This question involved multiple issues: the definition of fragility, its

mapping and the identification of possible solutions. Beyond the specific results, the case study was framed within the broader literature about terraced systems to discuss how it operationalised a system approach to the description and management of agro-hydrological infrastructures. The four lessons learned on the co-design of the assessment method and the re-design of management priorities highlight some perspectives for future research. In particular, the proposed GIS-based multicriteria assessment and the procedure for evaluating its validity could be applied to other agro-hydrological systems and other Mediterranean agricultural systems where soil and water management needs to be integrated at the watershed or landscape level.

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